

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B325
Date: 11 September 2007
Take Off 07:42:32
Landing: 11:49:03
Flight Time 4h 06m 31s

Campaign: NEON & SWS test

Operating Area: Wattisham & areas E&F

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM 1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Andreas Keil	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chem / CCM2	Bob Wells	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Shims / SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
9	IR camera	Joss Kent	Met Office
10	Mission Scientist 2	Stuart Newman	Met Office
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Flight Track:

B325 Track 11-SEP-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B325
 Date: 11 September 2007
 Project: NEON & SWS
 Location: Wattisham & North Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
071212		!	0.00 kft	126	system restart with correct flt no
071237		wow	0.00 kft	126	breaker made
071249		INU	0.00 kft	126	nav
071259		GIN	0.00 kft	126	recording
071414		neph	0.00 kft	126	zero
071427		heimann	0.00 kft	126	closed
071435		bbr	0.00 kft	126	extend
073617		ASP	0.00 kft	053	open
074232		T/O	-.01 kft	212	Cranfield
074544		Video	5.3 kft	037	#1 spotter, #2 UP start
075135		WAS	11.0 kft	062	bottle 31
075446		heimann	11.0 kft	061	open
075455		bbr	11.0 kft	061	retract
075506		WAS	11.0 kft	061	bottle 32
080332	080542	Profile 1	10.2 - 7.1 kft	144	
080440		bbr	8.7 kft	144	extend
080612		bbr	7.0 kft	240	retract
080811	080951	Run 1.1	7.0 kft	228	7000ft qfe1014
080929		overhead	7.0 kft	231	
081304		nev	7.0 kft	043	zero
081405		JW	7.0 kft	043	zero
081601		heimann	7.0 kft	043	cal 06
082650	083527	Profile 2	7.0 - -.02 kft	239	missed approach Wattiham 50ft
083132		exit cloud	3.0 kft	235	
084017	084131	Run 2.1	0.39 - 0.51 kft	042	500 ft qfe 1014
084059		overhead	0.47 kft	043	
084506	084645	Run 2.2	0.40 - 0.52 kft	233	500ft 1014 qfe
084616		!	0.47 kft	231	start
084638		!	0.48 kft	231	end
085031	085203	Run 3.1	1.0 - 0.99 kft	046	1000ft qfe 1014
085132		!	1.0 kft	042	start
085154		!	1.00 kft	040	end
085546	085722	Run 3.2	0.95 - 0.96 kft	234	
085653		!	0.96 kft	228	start
085715		!	0.94 kft	230	end
085920		Heimann	0.92 kft	232	cal09
090205	090422	Run 3.3	0.95 kft	044	
090350		!	0.95 kft	042	start
090417		!	0.95 kft	040	end
090512		qfe	0.95 kft	073	1015
090814	091010	Run 3.4	0.94 kft	231	
090932		!	0.93 kft	230	start
091001		!	0.94 kft	229	end
091154		heimann	0.94 kft	265	cal 09
091348		video	0.94 kft	079	#3 spotter, #4 UFC
091528	091713	Run 3.5	0.93 kft	045	
091640		!	0.94 kft	044	start
091706		!	0.93 kft	041	end
091849	092756	Profile 3	1.1 - 10.0 kft	043	
092838		!	10.0 kft	026	repositioning
093521	095211	Profile 5	10.0 - -.28 kft	314	500ft/min
NOTE: no profile 4!					
094115		P5	4.4 kft	315	interrupted
094306		P5	4.4 kft	134	restart
095406	100422	Run 4.1	-.12 - -.26 kft	303	
100422	100618	Profile 6	-.09 - 0.78 kft	310	start as end r4.1
100814	101805	Run 5.1	0.81 kft	118	500' below cloud base
101819	102113	Profile 7	0.87 - 2.2 kft	124	

102309	103231	Run 6.1	2.2 kft	305
103231	103403	Profile 8	2.2 - 2.9 kft	313
103532	104537	Run 7.1	2.9 kft	115
104538	104913	Profile 9	2.9 - 5.0 kft	119
104621		Video	3.3 kft	119 #5 FWD #6 UFC
105010	105448	Run 8.1	5.0 kft	159 into sun
105617	110116	Run 8.2	5.0 kft	343 down sun
110206	110906	Run 8.3	5.0 kft	258
111035	111534	Run 8.4	5.0 kft	072
111612		!	5.0 kft	007 end of science
113857		bbr	4.4 kft	248 extend
113920		heimann	4.0 kft	248 cal09
113934		heimann	3.7 kft	248 closed
114003		ASP	3.1 kft	248 closed
114903		Land	-.03 kft	028 Cranfield

B325 Track 11-SEP-07

SORTIE BRIEF

Flight B325 (NEON over Wattisham + SWS testing)

11 Sep 2007

Trial Objectives

1. To validate the NEON TDA using the IR camera looking at a runway.
(As done at previous NEON sorties during VISURB, CAPEX)
2. To do SWS testing.

Take off

8:30 a.m. local time.

Location

1. Over and nearby the Runway of Wattisham Airfield. / 2. Over North Sea.

Weather

Ideally for 1: Totally cloud free conditions during and several hours before the flight.

Instrumentation Required

IR camera, core temperature, water vapour, ARIES, Heimann, Cloud Physics.

- IR camera: Use wide angle lens unless otherwise stated, use 1 to 5 Hz data acquisition
- Video recording : IR spotter camera and upward video

Hints

- Note that in order to keep the runway in the field of view of the IR camera all altitudes will need to be flown at exact heights above the surface and not at flight levels (table 1).
- Try to get the same part of the runway in the FoV at every altitude, starting with NE end of runway, to be adapted during flight if necessary.
- Try to keep a roughly constant roll angle (ideally near zero) when taking photos of runway.
- M/S 1: Get information on ground-based visibility a few times during the Wattisham trial from ground-based "Wattisham Met Man" (94674-8227)

Flight Pattern

1. Take off and transit to Wattisham airfield/runway, to arrive at 10,000ft.
--- Neon over/nearby runway: -----
2. Fly over runway at 10,000ft, try to get IR cam images of the runway (concrete, tarmac, grass to be in the Field of View of the IR cam), ideally full length of runway;
- repeat if unsuccessful -
3. PROFILE = descent down to Wattisham airfield, ending with a missed approach over the runway;
4. SLR at 500ft: 1. directly along/over runway; 2. along/over grass path parallel to runway (hereby fly right of runway to allow IR cam to look at runway);
5. Repeated runs at 1,000ft, ideally scanning along the runway with IR cam (use 20-degree approaches if necessary only, see Fig. 3);
6. PROFILE up to 10,000ft;
7. Repeat 2 to 6 as time permits.
- At about T+3.5 hours stop NEON + start SWS testing: -----
8. Transit to operating area (North Sea, 15mins)
9. Profile descent in to operating area to lowest permitted altitude at 1000ft/min reducing to 500ft/min 1000ft above cloud deck (15mins)

10. Straight and level run at 100ft oriented across wind , advecting with the wind (10 mins)
Sections 3 to 11 should be performed to create a vertical stack of runs but each run is allowed to advect with the wind. The idea being to sample the same column of air/cloud.
 11. Profile ascent to level 500ft below cloud base at 500ft/min (5 mins)
 12. Straight and level run oriented across wind (10 mins)
 13. Profile to level just in base of cloud at 500ft/min (5 mins)
 14. Straight and level run in cloud base (10mins)
 15. Profile to level just below cloud tops at 500ft/min (5 mins)
 16. Straight and level run just below cloud tops (10 mins)
 17. Profile to level 1000ft above cloud tops (5 mins)
 18. Two reciprocal straight and level runs above cloud (each of 10 mins)
 19. Profile down to lowest permitted altitude and repeat items 10 to 18 if time allows.
- At about T+5 hours -----
20. Transit back to Cranfield.
 21. Landing.
- Total time: about 5.5 hours**

Fig. 1: View of Wattisham runway NW end, from 500ft.

“20-degree approach” - top view -

Fig. 3: “20 degree approach” instead of flying parallel to the runway to get runway in FoV of the IR cam.

IR camera:

- Get runway in FoV of the IR camera during the 20-degree approaches (cp. Fig. 3), check during flight using IR cam and spotter camera. **If this fails, run must be repeated!**
- Record both, IR camera and spotter camera pics.

Appendix A: Height – Distance Conversion

The horizontal shift S of flight legs parallel to the runway to keep the runway in the view of the IR camera is dependent on the angle Y the camera is looking below the horizontal and the flight height H:

$$S \text{ (nautical miles)} = H \text{ (ft)} / \tan(Y) * 0.3048 * 0.54E-03$$

Assuming IR camera view = 35 degrees down the horizontal:

(Use EXCEL sheet to compute distances for other angles, <http://metresearch.net/CAESAR/>)

Ideal NEON flight levels marked with an X	Flight Height (ft)	Displacement right of runway (nautical miles)	Flight Height (km)	Displacement (km)	Displacement (statute miles)	IR camera viewing distance (km)
missed approach: X	0	0	0	0	0	0
X	500	0.118	0.152	0.218	0.135	0.12
X	1000	0.235	0.305	0.435	0.270	0.53
	2000	0.470	0.610	0.871	0.541	
X	3000	0.705	0.914	1.306	0.811	1.59
	4000	0.940	1.219	1.741	1.082	
X	5000	1.175	1.524	2.176	1.352	2.66
	6000	1.410	1.829	2.612	1.623	
	7000	1.645	2.134	3.047	1.893	
	8000	1.880	2.438	3.482	2.164	4.25
	9000	2.115	2.743	3.918	2.434	
X	10000	2.350	3.048	4.353	2.705	5.31
	12000	2.821	3.658	5.224	3.246	
(X)	14000	3.291	4.267	6.094	3.787	7.44
	27000	6.346	8.230	11.753	7.303	

Table 1: Displacement for straight and level runs to keep the runway in the FoV of the IR camera (Y=35 degrees).

Fig. 4: Displacement graph (Y=35 degrees).

B325 - Mission Scientist Debrief

Date: 11 Sep 2007
Mission Scientist: Andreas Keil

Objective: SWS testing in Sc + NEON flight over Wattisham Airfield

This flight was intended to be a full scale Neon validation flight over Wattisham airfield (3.5 to 4 hours), with the add-on of some testing of the SWS in Sc over the North Sea (rest of time). Two staff were to perform ground based-measurements (Heitronics + cone) at Wattisham Airfield.

Weather conditions:

The forecast conditions were excellent for Neon, being cloudless skies over Wattisham throughout the night from 10 to 11 Sep and during the morning of 11 Sep, leading to well-defined conditions for surface heating. At 5:30 a.m. there was still no cloud over Wattisham, and the forecaster there expected hardly any cloud, and if any Sc patches would appear that those would burn off quickly. However, when arriving over Wattisham there were 8/8 Sc (20 miles away still cloud-free). These clouds did not burn off (ground-based staff reported 7/8 Sc at 11:30 a.m.). Sc was thin but mostly solid.

Flight Execution:

Take off: 8:30 local.

Mission started towards Wattisham were one over-flight at 7000ft was performed, but as there were no cloud gaps over Wattisham airfield the IR camera did see nothing of it. In turn, a vertical profile with missed approach over the airfield was flown, followed by successful ARIES-runs at 500ft over runway and adjacent grass path. After several unsuccessful attempts one successful flight at 1000ft parallel to the runway was performed, scanning along the full length of the runway with the IR camera. Simultaneously, the ground-based team conducted measurements of grass, concrete and asphalt temperatures at the airfield. As weather conditions did not improve, the Neon flight was aborted afterwards.

Then the aircraft was flown toward the North Sea to make SWS test around the Sc cloud fields present there. Though the Sc clouds were thicker there than over land, some searching had to be performed to have thick enough clouds useful for SWS.

Landing: about 12:40 local.

Summary:

Altogether a useful flight for testing SWS (about 2.5 hours flight time). Neon part was cut short (about 1.5 hours) and acquired IR camera data of low use for Neon.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.325**
FAAM © 2004

Date 11/9/07

Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	NEON over	Wattisham +		SWS	- Testing in Sc over North Sea
	- IR cam	(700)	→	wide-angle lense	
	- SWS	(Jan)			
7:42:33		V/O		from Cranfield	
7:45:44					start video rec'g (#1 path, #2 up)
8:05:30	#1.1	7ft			center down Airfield Wattisham
8:26:25	P1	7ft	→	runway	8/8 Sc - IR sees nothing above Sc
8:36		Missed		Approach over runway Wattisham (50ft)	
					Sc from 3.0 - 3.8 ft
8:41:00-20		2.1	→		50ft above runway
8:46:16-36		2.2	→		50ft above grass, incl. IR successful capturing runway (still DP to 7/8 Sc transducers)
8:52	1000ft	3.1	→		Failure (IR did not see runway)
8:57	"	3.2	"	"	"
8:59					Clouds breaking up → 7/8 - 6/8 over Wattisham
9:03:50					(turnover for NEON, tre thin for SWS)
	1000ft	3.3	→		Failure (edge of r/w)
9:09:31	"	3.4	→		Success! (full length)
9:17:04	"	3.5	→		Failure // Break of NEON
9:18	P3				Heading towards N-Sea in search for thicker Sc

ON:

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WS:

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.325**
FAAM © 2004

Date 11/9/07

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)															
09:45		3.7R	126	53.6/11.1	Sc: top = 3.7R ft, base = 2.4R ft (variable) 7/8 Sc															
09:52:10		50ft																		
10:08-10:18		0.8R			10 min leg 500ft below cloud															
10:23-10:33		2.2R			10 min leg 2200ft cloud base															
10:35-10:45		2.9R			" 2500ft above cloud															
10:50-10:55		5R			into sun															
10:50-11:01		5R			clear sun															
11:02-11:05		"			across sun															
11:10-11:15		"																		
<u>End of Screen</u>																				
Landing at Cranfield at <u>11:45</u> <u>pm</u> .																				
<u>together</u>																				
<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 30%;">Flight Time</td> <td style="width: 10%; text-align: center;">≈</td> <td style="width: 15%; text-align: center;">4</td> <td style="width: 10%; text-align: center;">h</td> <td style="width: 35%;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neon</td> <td style="text-align: center;">≈</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.5</td> <td style="text-align: center;">h</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>PWS</td> <td style="text-align: center;">≈</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2.5</td> <td style="text-align: center;">h</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>						Flight Time	≈	4	h		Neon	≈	1.5	h		PWS	≈	2.5	h	
Flight Time	≈	4	h																	
Neon	≈	1.5	h																	
PWS	≈	2.5	h																	
⇒ problems with mouse control M/S1 laptop																				
↓ to solve: -reboot -do <u>not</u> hold on left fw edge! (unbelievable, but works!)																				

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 325

Date: 11/09/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 06:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
08:05:50	10	0.07	2	1	1											End of Profile 1 @ FL070	
08:08:20																Run 1.1 @ 7000'	
08:09:00	10	0.07		1													
08:10:00	10	0.07		1													
08:11:00	7	0.07		1	1											End of Run 1.1	
08:26:48	20	0.07		1												Start Profile 2 from 7000'	
08:28:09	20	0.07		1												6000'	
08:29:18	25	0.07		1												5000'	
08:30:15	15	0.07		1												4000'	
08:31:31	30	0.10	68	15	2	1										3000'	
08:32:40	70	0.07		15	2											2000'	
08:34:00	90	0.07		20	1											1000'	
08:35:35	130	0.07	69	20	1											End of Profile 2 @ 50'	
08:40:20																Start Run 2.1 @ 500'	
08:41:00	100	0.07	70	20	1												
08:41:40																End of Run 2.1	
08:44:25																Start Run 2.2 @ 500'	
08:45:00	85	0.07	71	20	1												
08:46:41																End of Run 2.2	
08:50:30																Start Run 3.1 @ 1000'	
08:51:00	60	0.07	73	15	2												
08:52:16																End of Run 3.1	
0855:45																Start Run 3.2 @ 1000'	
08:56:00	40	0.07	74	10	2												
08:57:40																End of Run 3.2	
09:02:08																Start Run 3.3 @ 1000'	
09:03:00	90	0.08	77	15	2												
09:04:50																End of Run 3.3	
09:08:14																Start Run 3.4 @ 1000'	
09:09:00	50	0.07	78	20	2												
09:10:30																End of Run 3.4	
09:14:30																Start Run 3.5 @ 1000'	
09:15:00	95	0.07	80	15	1												
09:17:30																End of Run 3.5	
09:18:50	50	0.07	81	15	1											Start Profile 4 from 1000'	
09:19:31	22	0.07		15	1											2000'	
09:20:30	65	0.14	130	3000	2000	25	150	25							1	3000'	
09:21:40	10	0.07	205		Noise											4000'	
09:22:35	10	0.07			Noise											5000'	
09:23:42	10	0.07			Noise											6000'	
09:24:46	5	0.07			Noise											7000'	
09:25:49	7	0.08		1	2											8000'	
09:26:52	15	0.07		1	1											9000'	

PCASP Reference Volts = 9.6 V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.15V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.0 CC/Sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.0V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.12V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12 mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = - 3.4V		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 325

Date: 11/09/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 06:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:27:53	10	0.08	205	1	1											End of Profile 4 @ FL100	
09:35:20	10	0.07		1	1											Start Profile 5 from FL100	
09:36:30	15	0.08		1												FL090	
09:37:20	10	0.07		1												FL080	
09:38:21	10	0.07		1												FL070	
09:39:22	8	0.08		1												FL060	
09:40:25	8	0.07														FL050	
09:43:54	15	0.08		1	Noise											FL040	
09:46:03	35	0.14	624	100	10	0.5										FL030	
09:47:30	40	0.08	696	100	5	1	500								1	FL020	
09:49:11	35	0.07	698	15	2											FL010	
09:52:25	30	0.07	699	10	1											End of Profile 5 @ 50'	
09:54:06																Start Run 4.1 @ 100'	
09:55:00	25	0.08		10	1												
09:57:00	45	0.07		10	1												
09:59:00	35	0.07		10	1												
10:01:00	30	0.07	701	15	1												
10:03:00	35	0.07		15	1												
10:04:22																End of Run 4.1 & Start Profile 6 from 100'	
10:06:17																End of Profile 6 @ FL007	
10:08:13																Start Run 5.1 @ FL007	
10:09:00	45	0.08	704	20	1												
10:11:00	35	0.07		20	1												
10:13:00	25	0.08	705	20	1												
10:15:00	30	0.07		10	1												
10:17:00	45	0.07	706	10	1												
10:18:05																End of Run 5.1 & Start Profile 7 from FL007	
10:18:45	35	0.07		15	2											FL010	
10:20:51	30	0.07	707	15	1											FL020	
10:21:10																End of Profile 7 @ FL021	
10:23:09																Start Run 6.1 @ FL021	
10:24:00	65	0.08	717	80	10	2	400	130	400						1		
10:26:00	50	0.07	718	20	5												
10:28:00	35	0.08	722	20	5												
10:30:00	25	0.07	723	20	3												
10:32:00	25	0.07		20	5												
10:32:31																End of Run 6.1 & Start Profile 8 from FL021	
10:34:04																End of Profile 8 @ FL029	
10:35:33																Start Run 7.1 @ FL029	
10:36:00	25	0.12	909	1000	900	20	100								1		
10:38:00	70	0.12	1065	2000	3000	20	200	40							1		
10:40:00	30	0.12	1200	2000	1000	20	150								1		
10:42:00	50	0.07	1219	80	10	3		15									

PCASP Reference Volts = 9.6 V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.15V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.0 CC/Sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -1.0V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.12V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12 mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = - 3.4V		

B325_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

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06:20:27.60 --- - - - -
06:20:27.60 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
06:20:27.60 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
06:20:27.60 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B325
06:20:27.60 --- - - - -
06:20:47.59 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:21:06.60 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:21:24.01 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:21:40.69 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
06:21:45.60 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
06:21:49.98 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 500ms to 100ms.
06:22:04.18 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:22:15.47 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:19.92 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:26.00 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:35.93 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:40.41 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:23:04.40 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:23:04.40 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:23:04.41 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:23:06.61 LSH - - - - Idling
06:23:06.61 SWS - - - - Idling
06:23:06.77 USH - - - - Idling
06:23:15.83 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:23:15.83 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:23:15.84 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:23:31.37 USH - - - - Idling
06:23:31.38 SWS - - - - Idling
06:23:31.41 LSH - - - - Idling
06:25:18.17 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:25:24.55 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:25:26.11 USH - - - - Idling
06:25:28.98 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:25:32.45 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:25:33.88 USH - - - - Idling
06:25:40.85 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:25:42.80 SWS - - - - Idling
06:25:44.93 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:25:46.36 LSH - - - - Idling
06:25:50.26 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:25:50.26 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:25:50.26 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
06:26:07.16 USH - - - - Idling
06:26:07.16 LSH - - - - Idling
06:26:07.24 SWS - - - - Idling
06:26:13.82 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:26:13.82 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:26:13.83 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:26:15.25 USH - - - - Idling
06:26:15.48 LSH - - - - Idling
06:26:15.65 SWS - - - - Idling
06:26:19.61 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:26:24.34 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:26:24.34 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:28:25.81 --- - - - - *** Peltiers 1 + 2 not working!! Cut out
                    switches checked
06:28:56.11 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
06:28:58.68 LSH - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
06:29:01.09 LSH - - - - Idling
06:29:10.02 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:29:42.33 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 100ms.
06:29:45.54 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 100ms.
06:29:47.08 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:29:48.51 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:30:31.64 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
06:30:33.07 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

```

06:30:36.17	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
06:30:40.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:30:41.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:30:46.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:30:46.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:30:46.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:30:49.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:30:51.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:31:09.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:31:11.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:31:12.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:31:14.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:33:36.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:33:36.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:33:36.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:33:38.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:33:38.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:33:38.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:34:41.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:34:41.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:34:41.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:58:15.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:58:15.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:58:15.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:58:16.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:58:16.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:58:17.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:58:43.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:58:43.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:58:44.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
06:59:58.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:59:58.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
06:59:58.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:00:00.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:00.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:00:00.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:28:03.29	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:28:06.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:06.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:06.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:28:08.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:28:08.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:28:08.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:28:14.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:14.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:28:14.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:30:18.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:30:19.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:30:22.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:30:24.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:30:31.30	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:30:36.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:30:37.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:31:12.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:31:13.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:31:16.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:31:17.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:31:20.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:31:21.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:31:39.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:31:39.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:31:39.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:31:44.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:31:44.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:31:44.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:31:45.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:31:45.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:31:46.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:31:48.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

07:31:48.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:31:48.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:59:11.28	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:59:16.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:59:16.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:59:16.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:59:17.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:59:17.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:59:18.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:59:20.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:59:20.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:59:21.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:59:26.71	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
08:00:01.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler temp 12 C
08:00:42.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** Height 11000' thin Sc below
08:01:00.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** Clear above
08:01:21.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:01:23.75	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:01:27.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:01:29.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:01:31.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:01:46.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:01:54.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:01:55.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:02:01.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:02:03.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:02:22.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:02:24.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:02:26.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:14:05.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:14:07.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:14:09.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:14:18.58	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
08:14:20.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:14:21.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:14:23.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:23:54.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:23:57.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:23:59.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:01.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:24:04.82	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
08:24:07.77	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
08:24:09.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:24:10.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:24:13.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:27:23.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** Entering cloud in
08:30:39.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** Entering cloud in P2 descent, tops at 3800'
08:31:36.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** exit cloud, base at 3000'
08:32:06.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:32:08.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:32:09.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:32:12.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:32:23.14	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
08:32:25.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:32:26.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:32:28.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:35:26.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** End profile 2 50' over Wattisham
08:37:02.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:37:02.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:37:03.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:37:04.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:37:04.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:37:04.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:37:05.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:37:06.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:37:06.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:37:22.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** NEON part of flight
08:37:29.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

08:37:29.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:37:29.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:53:46.79	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:53:51.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:53:51.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:53:51.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:53:52.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:53:52.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:53:52.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:43:07.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:07.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:08.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:43:09.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:43:09.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:43:09.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:43:11.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:11.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:11.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:34.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start P5
09:44:49.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top at 3700'
09:46:27.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base at 2800'
09:46:51.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** note sws pointing nad since recent start of measurement
09:52:11.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile at 50'
09:52:15.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:52:15.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:52:15.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:52:17.82	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:52:21.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:21.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:21.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:22.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:52:22.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:52:22.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:52:42.57	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
09:52:45.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:45.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:45.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:54:16.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run at 100' R4.1
09:54:45.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:54:47.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:54:48.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:54:54.35	USH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
09:54:58.10	USH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
09:55:05.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:09.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:55:11.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:15.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:55:17.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:19.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:55:22.58	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
09:55:25.44	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
09:55:29.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:34.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:55:37.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:57:19.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:57:22.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:57:25.38	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
09:57:28.12	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
09:57:29.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:57:32.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:57:34.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:57:37.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:23.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sol Zen = 54 deg
10:04:23.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
10:04:27.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:27.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:28.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:29.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:04:29.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:04:29.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:04:30.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:32.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:34.84	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:04:34.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:39.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:04:39.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:04:39.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:04:39.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:41.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:44.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:44.68	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:04:52.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:04:52.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:04:52.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:05:08.78	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
10:05:12.08	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
10:05:14.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:05:15.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:06:17.38	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:06:20.20	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:06:21.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:06:23.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:06:25.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:06:25.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:06:25.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:06:26.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:06:26.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:06:30.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:30.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:31.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:08:15.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run at 700'
10:10:53.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:07.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
10:18:14.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:18:14.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:18:14.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:18:16.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:17.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:17.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:17.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:18:18.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:18:22.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:18:32.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:32.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:32.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:28.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run at 2500' R6.1 just in base
10:32:31.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
10:32:36.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:36.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:37.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:39.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:39.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:39.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:39.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:40.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:44.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:44.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:44.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:44.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:35:05.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run at 2900' R7.1
10:35:05.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:05.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:06.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:07.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:07.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:07.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:07.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:35:08.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:12.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:14.17	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
10:35:17.38	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
10:35:21.93	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:35:24.93	USH	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:35:29.58	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 200ms.
10:35:32.48	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 200ms.
10:35:35.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:35.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:35.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:37.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:38.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:39.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:35:44.13	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:35:46.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:35:46.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:35:46.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:37.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
10:45:40.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:40.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:40.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:42.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:42.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:42.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:43.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:44.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:45.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:10.75	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:46:16.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:16.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:16.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:53.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:47:54.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:47:57.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:48:00.56	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:48:04.11	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:48:08.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:09.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:48:11.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:24.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:48:26.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:27.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:48:30.39	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
10:48:33.04	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
10:48:34.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:36.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:48:38.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:18.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start into sun run 4900' R8.1
10:50:21.89	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:50:35.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:50:36.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:50:38.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:50:41.19	LSH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:50:44.03	LSH	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:50:46.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:50:47.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:50:49.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:46.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
10:54:51.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:51.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:51.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:53.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:53.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:53.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:54.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:54.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:55.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:54:58.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

10:54:58.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:54:58.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:55:42.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:42.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:42.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:15.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run 8.2 5000' out of sun
11:01:17.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
11:01:20.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:01:20.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:01:20.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:01:20.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:01:22.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:22.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:22.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:01:23.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:01:24.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:01:24.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:01:27.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:27.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:27.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:39.62	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:02:06.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run 8.3 at 5000'
11:02:20.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** across sun
11:09:08.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
11:09:11.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:11.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:11.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:13.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:13.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:13.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:13.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:14.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:15.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:23.15	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 40ms.
11:09:25.68	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 40ms.
11:09:33.13	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
11:09:35.85	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
11:09:41.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:41.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:41.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:43.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:43.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:43.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:09:47.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:47.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:47.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:35.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run 8.4 across sun
11:15:35.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
11:15:42.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:42.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:42.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:43.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:43.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:43.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:44.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:45.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:15:45.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:16:02.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** end science
11:16:08.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:16:08.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:16:08.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

ARIES flight log

Flight: B325

page 1 of 3

Date: 11/9/07 Operator(s): S.M. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NEON over Wattisham

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
061800		1x60	C	C	7.3	30.9	GROUND TESTS
061835		1x60	H	C	7.2	30.5	
061914		60x1	N	C	7.2	31.0	Looking at the pan
061952		1x60	C	C			
062026		1x60	H	C	7.1	30.8	
062112		60x1	Z	O	70.9	31.0	Clear skies above
062156		1x60	C	C	7.2	31.3	
062230		1x60	H	C	7.2	30.4	
074234	TAKE-OFF						
075300							passing from clear over edge of Sc
080846	R1 ↓	1x60	C	C	70.9	30.9	Over 8/8 Sc
080923	7000ft	1x60	H	C	70.7	30.9	
081000		60x1	N	C	71.2	30.7	Sc below; then turn
081038		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.7	
081115		1x60	H	C	70.8	30.9	
083613		1x60	C	C	70.7	30.4	} manoeuvres
083646		1x60	H	C	70.5	30.7	
083728		240x1	N	C	70.8	30.6	083750 turn till end
083933	500ft	240x1	N	C	70.6	30.6	level 084057 runway - 084121
084138	(R2.1)	1x60	C	C	70.8	30.6	
084211		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.7	
084508	R2.2	240x1	N	C	70.8	31.0	grass 084615 - 084638 (abort)
084655		1x60	C	C	70.8	31.0	climbing
084728		1x60	H	C	70.8	31.1	" 1000 ft
084812	1000ft	1x60	C	C	70.5	30.6	turning
084847	R3.1	1x60	H	C	70.8	30.5	"
085031		180x1	N	C	70.8	30.8	Ston 085132 - 085153 ←
085209		1x60	C	C	70.8	30.9	turning
085243		1x60	H	C	70.8	30.6	
085557	R3.2	180x1	N	C	70.7	30.7	Repeat 085643 - 085715 ←

IR camera failed view

IR camera missed runway again

ARIES flight log

Flight: B325 page 2 of 3

Date: 11/9/07 Operator(s): S.M. NEWMAN Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: Wattisham

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Comments
085812		1x60	C	C	70.8	30.4	
085846		1x60	H	C	71.1	31.0	
085922		1x60	C	C	70.8	30.6	
085958		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.7	
090251	R3.3	180x1	N	C	70.9	30.7	Still Sc overhead 090350-090416
090450		1x60	C	C	70.7	30.8	turn
090526		1x60	H	C	70.6	30.9	
090750		1x60	C	C	70.6	31.0	
090823		1x60	H	C	70.9	30.8	
090928		120x1	N	C			090933 - Successful IR camera
091036		1x60	C	C	70.9	30.5	
091110		1x60	H	C	71.0	29.9	
091241		1x60	C	C	70.6	30.4	
091316		1x60	H	C	71.1	30.8	
091641	1000ft	90x1	N	C			S to N too far away in IR camera
091734		1x60	C	C	71.0	31.0	Still Sc overhead
091808		1x60	H	C	71.0	30.8	
091850	P3						End NEON → N. sea Sc for SWS DRS 092245 = ARIES 092244
104924		1x60	C	C	70.7	30.7	Above Sc over N. sea
105003	R8.1	1x60	H	C	70.9	30.7	Into-sun run for SWS
105039		240x1	N	C	70.8	30.8	Uniform deck of Sc below
105247		1x60	C	C	70.9	30.9	
105324		1x60	H	C	71.0	30.7	
105623		1x60	C	O			Down sun - shutter open throughout as test of stability
105657		1x60	H	O	70.6	31.2	
105740	R8.2	240x1	Z	O	70.9	30.5	Looks clear above
105950		1x60	C	O	70.7	31.0	
110033		1x60	H	O	70.8	30.7	
110208	R8.3	1x60	C	C	71.0	30.9	Across-sun for SWS, just above Sc
110242		1x60	H	C	71.0	30.6	

07908002826

IR CAMERA FLIGHT LOG

Flight No. 13325
 Date 4/09/07
 Fitted Lens 28 mm
 Active NUC 05012006 NOV3 05/04/2006
 BPM Filename DBTEST1

Campaign NEEN
 Operator Joss
 Camera Angle 35 Degs down

Source Ref. Temp.	Hot <u>5</u> °C
	Cold <u>40</u> °C

DATA RECORDING	Run	Height	Remarks
Start Time	Stop Time	Number	
CALIBRATION			
	Temp °C		
061057	13.2		
061757	14.3		
061857	17.8		
061957	20.6		
062057	23.0		
062157	25.3		
062257	27.4		
062357	29.5		
062457	31.5		
062557	33.4		
062657	35.2		
062757	36.9		
062857	38.7		
062957	40.3		
063057	41.9		
Did not record calibration			
WATTSHAM QFE = 1014 mb.			
R1.1 080811	080957	R1.1	700'
083512		P	50'
084104	084122	R2.1	300'
084901	084633	R2.2	500'
085130		R3.1	1000'
085638	085722	R3.2	1000'
090330	090430	R3.3	1000'
090855	091007	R3.4	1000'
091109	0916	R3.5	1000'
130648	23.0		
130748	24.7		
0848	28.1		
0948	30.9		
1048	33.1		
1148	35.4		
1248	37.5		
1348	39.7		
1448	41.5		
1548	43.5		

Too much cloud, no view of airfield.
 Approach over Wattsham
 Along runway run for ALTES.
 No good views (1 bank)
 dust in view
 Just in view @ end - too far away.
 Good view all the way down.
 Missed ok.
 Ground Cal

B325

Security 0745L
T/O 0830L
LAND 1350L

BOTRES.
LHOW
LNUA
~~DEFS~~
LGIN
LNEPH
LPSAP

HEIMANN ✓
BBR ✓
VIDEO ✓
ASP ✓

land Cranfield
11:49:03

13:30h de brief.

O3 pump
PFC

Flight:

B325

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 11/10/2007
17:34:36**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

11/10/2007 09:12:36

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B325

Date: 11/09/2007

Instruments

1. PSAP data recording problem, not yet understood
2. O3 pump running hot – service required?
3. Forward facing camera window dirty – cleaned preflight

Aircraft

nil

Satcom-H Calls

2 (NEON)

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B325:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log and no PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page – DUFF data

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	4 Dec 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Spotter Cameras
2 x Upward Facing Cameras
1 x Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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